

LEADING CHOICE: SERVANT LEADERSHIP, FAITH, GOVERNANCE AND DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA.

¹OKEZIE, GOODLUCK NWOKOMA, PhD and

²OGAH CHRISTOPHER OSIMHEN, DMin.

okezieg@babcock.edu.ng; +2349048503217

ogahch@babcock.edu.ng; +2348133802415

^{1,2} Religious studies Department, Babcock University

Corresponding Author: okezieg@babcock.edu.ng

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20594149>

Abstract

This study investigated the combination of faith in governance in-view of tangible development outcomes based on the background of Servant Leadership with Leading Choice as their derivative. Consequently, the study examined values such as openness, honesty, accountability, diligence, dispatch, citizen participation, freewill and initiative as factors of good governance. The theoretical basis is the Servant style of leadership. The Content Analysis research design was used to explain the characteristics of faith, governance and development. To establish what happens in their relationships. The qualitative methodology and techniques were adopted to identify patterns and trends from the variables under study. It was found that the national development indices of Nigeria improved when governance is faith-based, and followers have learnt to freely make effective and efficient choices in the workplace. This improved performance in each organization and increased the economic development, the human capital development index and the social capital of Nigeria. This study has implications on academic endeavors and practical governance in Nigeria. It has become clear that Servant Leadership is critical in implementing faith principles in the process of Governance, in expectation of Development.

Key Words – *Leading Choice, Servant Leadership, Faith, Governance and Development.*

Introduction

Literature is saturated with research findings and conclusions that support charismatic, transactional, transformational, autocratic, laissez-Faire, situational, democratic, servant and participative leadership styles. Except for servant leadership, none of these styles came close to the creation of a leader from a follower, through the follower's personal choices because of the leaders' influences, (Shiundu, 2024). Servant Leadership is required to connect Faith and Governance, towards the development of the Nigerian state. The Servant Leader has faith in God and depends on Him in the process of leading, (Tanugraha et al., 2024). Hence, the style will be helpful in the leader's belief and the values that matter in the process of leadership and influence. This makes the leader provide governance that allows the follower to feel free to make personal decisions in the work process, (Shiundu, 2024). This may have implications for the development of the followers, the organization and the nation. Such development is measured by the personal growth of the follower. Hence, from Santiago-Torner, et al., (2024), the follower needs more emotional balance and moral independence. This will be possible if the follower makes

leadership choices freely and experiences a higher living standard. On the side of the organization, there is need for sustainable development. This is based on the adequacy of economic growth, social and environmental expectations. A country without these factors may not experience economic efficiency, social welfare and high living standards.

The Servant leader focuses on the growth and the development needs of the followers, (Jiang & Wei, 2024). This is reflected in this study in that the followers need to be free to make choices. The leader must allow them to make very important and corporate decisions, without the stick of transactions. The absence of this, as is the case in other traditional leadership styles, the follower will lack the ability to lead self. Though there are consequences for good and bad decisions, they should not be set as traps for the follower. Rather, every decision and action is based on love for the leader and the organizational services, (Cundiff, 2022). So, without the fear of failure nor the glory of praise, the follower freely makes decisions on behalf of the leader, for the organization, even at great risk, as was the case in the experiences of many of the disciples of Jesus. In the context of leading choice, the Servant leader influences the followers to lead themselves, by granting them opportunities to freely make critical decisions in the concerns of the organization.

The bible basis for the study

Many secular researchers have concluded that God is a deist. God was not absent from the world after creation, He has never been, (Herranz de Rafael & Fernández-Prados, 2022). He will never be. Hence, after giving humanity the freedom to choose either good or evil, [Genesis 2: 16,17]. He left Adam and Eve by themselves to freely decide what to do. In the above sense, God was leading change. In fact, He is still leading change by leaving the world in the hands of men and women to make leadership decisions about the earth. Even though God knew better, but leaving humanity in charge of the world is an act of faith in the human family, to establish and teach leading choice. Jesus hoped that leaders will provide humble governance, within the concept of leading change, with the expected outcome of wholistic development of the world and its inhabitants. After training the 12 apostles for three years and half, though they seem not to have understood their task, yet Jesus left the evangelistic world to them (Baba, 2022). In his study, Orgu (2020) reviewed that the promise of the Holy Spirit was left to their choice to accept or reject Him. The result of their choice is evident in our current world. Though the whole world is not yet ripe for harvest, we are still free to lead in the choice of where we will spend eternity. Consequently, the principle of Leading Choice is a divine ordination.

Theoretical framework

In this study, Faith, Governance and Development form a very important structure of the theoretical framework, of which, Leading Choice is their nucleus. This allows for the combination of leadership theories and faith-based conjectures. Servant Leadership theory is the best fit to this framework. Leading Choice encapsulates the intentional persuasion made by leaders to provide progressive direction, encourage citizenship behaviors and chat a moral compass for followers to evoke the traits of faith in them. This leads to Governance, which according to Sánchez-Soriano et al. (2014), structures the operational process of Leading Choice. Essentially, Governance provides faith with the platform for leadership to manifest rules of law, transparency, accountability and responsibility. Good governance is supportive of just policies, trustworthy leadership and equitable resources allocation. These are factors of development that produces high human development, economic growth and development, social unity and national

stewardship. The foregoing process is the transformational line from leadership to national development. At the level of transformation, the process has become sustainable and replicable.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

Source: Okezie and Ogah, Theoretical Framework, 2025.

In its practice and application, the Servant Leadership theory allows leadership to influence followers to transit from selfishness to selflessness, servanthood and team spirit. This transformation is very important particularly in Nigeria, where there is lack of mutual trust and governance process is manipulative and corrupt. According to Ogbe (2025), Servant Leadership will cause leaders to think strategically, govern ethically using disciplined policy implementations.

Consequently, leadership style makes it possible for stakeholders to be directed towards one vision, taking along principles of teamplay, service and development purpose. In his emphasis, Onyeulo and Okeke (2024) argues that Servant leadership leads to motivation, ethical behavior and national development. Their presentation shows that national development is dependent on how leadership responds to ethics, organizational vision and giving of a sense of belongingness to all stakeholders through service and empathy. The combination of Servant leadership, faith and Governance is a study at the sociopolitical complexity of the Nigerian state. This is particularly relevant in a country of multi-religious landscape, where faith has huge influence on society and governance. Therefore, there is the need to sync faith with governance. Leading Choice, which is the center of the nexus, directs attention to ethical leadership based on humility and Bible spirituality.

Ethics and spirituality are based on individuals. When the individual has been converted, this transformation produces principles of honesty, integrity, transparency and accountability. If the leader has been affected, then there will be a platform for the improvement of governance, which will lead to development and at the same time, reduce the cost of corruption. Hence Gbinder (2023), affirms that Christian education has a direct positive effect on Governance. The point is that faith is not passive, but rather a steppingstone for ethical governance. Hence, Udeagha and Nwamah (2023) emphasize that ethical behavior can influence public policy and thus, become a challenge to governance. This implies that not everything that the government does is ethical and faithful. Consequently, religion and governance should be symbiotic and complementary to each other. According to Nwanaju (2025), sometimes, religion can be manipulated to promote injustice and crises. These are possible due to fanatical approaches to religion and attempts to

exclude people from the democratic process due to their religious beliefs and practices. Therefore, the theoretical understanding of this study must align with the normative aspects of religion and the possibility of subjective and personal religion.

The theoretical symbiosis of governance and faith backgrounds the church-state separation. According to Duruji (2023), this separation is only a delineation of functions, but also a collaborative one, between the two entities. In this line of thought, religious operators can encourage developmental governance, by respecting and keeping to constitutional policies, rules and regulations of different levels of government. This will in turn improve the ethics of public office. This agrees with the conjecture of Democratic Theory. It addresses extant democratic problems, such as crises and violence by providing disciplined governance and encouraging the actions towards what ought to be (Ahlhaus, 2024). Democratic Theory lends credence to responsible governance. Hence, according to (Tudor, 2025), it allows for accountable political leadership, freedom of speech and the strengthening of institutions. The relevance of transparency is a direct outcome of Bible-based practices. Luka & Gofwan (2025) affirms that this will lead to a stewardship outlook on governance, which then positively reflects on the public sector, to produce pareto optimality and social wellbeing. This proves the theoretical thesis to be true, that the consonance of religion and governance will add up to economic growth and development.

Methodology and design

The design of the study was based on Content Analysis (Rojahn et al., 2025). This involved the analysis of the Servant leadership style. This was used to identify relevant patterns, themes and meanings that are necessary for the conclusion of leading choice style, backgrounded by faith in God and a just governance, with the expected outcome of development. The data collected is textual and analyzed thematically. Based on the background of Servant Leadership, which generates new value Adebisi & Oni (2019), such as Leading Choice, the purpose of this study is to find a nexus among Servant Leadership, Faith, Governance and Development in Nigeria.

Review of deterministic leadership styles

The idea of determination means that the leader leads out in every decision. He or she makes it. May be consulted before it is made. May influence the decision because of his or her personality, presence or manner of behavior. This does not mean that the followers do not make decisions. However, such decisions are not entirely free, because for all kinds of leadership styles, they are founded on transactional paybacks, of the stick and carrot. There are also no allowances for them to make corporate leadership decisions.

Autocratic style makes all decisions and does not give much of a chance for the followers to make contributions, Abdullah & Wahab (2023). In this process, the outcome is determined before the instruction is handed over to the team members. Democratic leadership allows the contributions of the followers; however, bureaucratic trappings erode such suggestions. To this extent, the final product of the decision will not represent, in any way, the contributions of the team members. Laissez-faire determines outcomes by mere chance, [Kristanto & Hartono, 2024]. It does not have direction, neither does the leader provide any for the followers. Thus, the contributions of the led are not asked for and may not even be needed. Though transformational style motivates the lead to getting involved in decision-making (Suryawan et al., 2021), but the

charismatic characteristic of the transformational leader may render such suggestions as unimportant and even useless. Transactional leadership style rewards and punishes performance and indolence, respectively. The involvement of the followers is based on the expected rewards and not on freedom of choice, [Feldman, 2017]. Situational leadership determines the style of leadership based on the subsisting situation. A charismatic leadership may identify a needed action and act on it without informing the team members, (Zhang et al., 2025). Thus, in situational leadership, the contribution of the followers is lagged. In the leadership styles of Autocratic, Democratic, Laissez-Faire, Transformational, Transactional and Situational, there is a clear dichotomy between the leader and the lead. In essence, it is easy to tell who the leader is and who is the follower. This is very deterministic and the status quo. In Leading Choice, Servant leadership is not deterministic. It is not easy to differentiate between the leader from the led and the followers have a stake and a very important say in the organization.

Faith, Governance and Development in Nigeria

The servant leader has faith in God. Based on the leader's beliefs and values, he or she provides governance that emphasizes the training of the followers to adopt the self-leading mode. Such a leadership model ensures the sustainable development of the led, the organization and the country. If it is true that the bane of Nigeria's economy is bad leadership, then the solution is the multiplication of Servant leaders in all the sectors and levels of leadership of the country. Servant Leadership and the practice of governance are important to make the institutions of a country strong and independent. The Servant Leadership of leadership provides the platform in which followers become selfless and hence combine efforts to achieve organizational goals, instead of their personal ones. In essence, no matter how small, one performed organizational objective is better than several individual goals of multiples of its employees. The interactions of theory and lived governance in a complex economy like Nigeria produce outcomes that transcends physical performance. Servant leaders motivate performance based on service and values, which results in improved governance and public goodwill. This is very relevant in Nigeria, with its corrupt leadership, ethnic biases and political manipulations. Hence, Servant leadership provides a practical escape route for good intentions, accountability, free will choices and performance. Empirically, when leadership is basically service-oriented, the relevant organization experiences commitment and service deliveries are standardized and efficient. This implies that theoretical constructions can be processed in actual institutional environments.

In a setting with multi-religious context, the Service Leadership will be challenged by various values, occasioned by different religious dynamics. This will present variant ethics, social behaviors and governance manifestations. Nevertheless, with leaders that understand such dynamics, within the labyrinth of beliefs, it is possible to find standard moral fabrics that can produce principles such as selflessness, integrity, stewardship and self-giving. These principles will enhance governance and entrench development (Offor et al., 2025). This is because religious principles have functional relationships with governance, however, this relationship is mediated by the leader and his or her ability to appropriate religious principles into the leadership process. The mediation of any type will either cause intersections or divergences. These two aspects are not only because of the leader, but also institutional differences of strength or weakness. At their intersections, the leader transforms the goals of the followers from self to that of the organization. This means that employees of an organization work as a team to achieve the plans of the organization (Azubuike et al., 2024). In this sense, the leader and the followers work as a united

team to carry out organizational tasks in ways that herald effective governance and development, not only of the origination, but also of the employees as well. This is what may be referred to as contributory progress, in which everyone gets appropriate and equitable part of prosperity. On the other hand, deviations between religion and governance will find the leader and the followers working at cross purposes. These will not venture toward the attainment of the objectives of the organization. Ayandibu (2024) reasoned that the likelihood of the employees working for their own selfish interests is much more likely, because there is a stress between leadership theory and its implementation. This will dissipate the resources of the organization and lead to ineffectiveness and inefficiency.

Conclusion

This study was backgrounded on Servant Leadership. It introduced the concept of Leading Choice as a process of leading followers to have the courage to make moral choices in a free and independent ways. This is initiated as Faith, which produces ethical Governance and finalizes at the development of the nation. The theoretical framework conjectured the functionality of Faith, Leading Choice, Governance and Development, within the context of Servant Leadership. This relationship may be mediated by the leader's ability to cause intersections or deviations between faith and leadership. The findings of this study draw critical attention to the need for Nigerian government to subject its national governance to religious scrutiny. It may be possible to replicate this study using leaders from different ethnic and religious backgrounds, such as Christians and Muslims. This will expose the empirical problems of political governance in Nigeria. With or without natural resources, the development of Nigeria depends solely on good leadership, of the servant style. Such leaders will focus on the growth and development of human capital. They will teach the citizens to lead themselves in a free and non-manipulative way. The outcome will be that the citizenry will have the moral power and independence of leading choice regarding what is morally right, at home, in the workplace, in the community, in state and the entire country.

Recommendations

The study found that except for the Servant Leadership, all other leadership styles are rather deterministic. In this sense, followers take all authority from the leader. This renders them to be very dependent on the leader. It will be appropriate for leaders to lead in ways that encourage independence of thoughts, words and actions in the followers. This will foster the spirit of initiative, problem-solving and creativity. In multiples of these, the Nation will be better for it, in performance of tasks, increased productivity and development.

Leading Choice is a direct outcome of Servant leadership. Under this process, Faith acts on Governance to lead to development. This relationship is not automatic. The leader should serve the followers leads through the example of humility, responsibility, service and selflessness. When this example is replicated in the led, they will in turn take up the goals of the organization as their own. At the end, the objectives of the organization will be met.

Nigeria is a corrupt state. It is a systemic problem. While Faith and Governance should remain separate, it is imperative to understand that the symbiosis between them may service the purpose of reducing the depth of corruption in Nigerian governance and at the same time strengthen the country's national institutions. This calls for leaders and followers to live up to the dictates of the

constitution, the byelaws, rules and regulations that govern the nation and all other levels of authority in the country.

References

- Adebisi, J. F., & Oni, C. S. (2019). Effect of population growth on economic development in Nigeria. *Humanities and Social Sciences*, 7(6), 197–207. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.hss.20190706.11>
- Abdullah, N., & Wahab, J. L. A. (2023). Principal autocratic leadership practice and its relationship with teacher job satisfaction in secondary schools of Jempol District, Negeri Sembilan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 13(9), 1945–1959. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBSS/v13-i9/18637>
- Ahlhaus, S. (2024). Contemporary democratic theory. *Contemporary Political Theory*, 24, 628–631. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41296-024-00734-9>
- Ayandibu, E. O. (2024). A review of transformational leadership and its impact on team, group, and departmental levels. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 13(12), 1083–1095.
- Azubuike, P. C., Imo, U. F., Ogbonna, C. K., Enyam, M. O., & Nwadiche, M. (2024). Harnessing religion in the pursuit of sustainable development in Nigeria. *Discover Global Society*, 2, Article 87. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44282-024-00119-8>
- Baba, E. D. (2022). The missionary model of Jesus: A case study for the church. *International Journal of Humanities, Social Sciences and Education*, 9(4), 190–200.
- Cundiff, N. L. (2022). Gender and organizational culture: Perceptions of leadership style and effectiveness. *Advancing Women in Leadership*, 41, 51–63.
- Duruji, S. U. (2023). Church–state relationship in Nigeria: Navigating the boundaries of governance and faith. *Advance Journal of Current Research*, 8(12), 1–17.
- Feldman, G. (2017). Making sense of agency: Belief in free will as a unique and important construct. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 11(1), e12293. <https://doi.org/10.1111/spc3.12293>
- Gbinde, S. A. (2023). Navigating the intersection of Christian teachings, social issues and modern challenges in Tiv Land. *African Journal of Humanities & Contemporary Education Research*, 13(1).
- Herranz de Rafael, G., & Fernández Prados, J. S. (2022). Explanation of the trends and recent changes in Spanish society regarding belief in God. *Religions*, 13(11), 1086. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel13111086>
- Jiang, X., & Wei, Y. (2024). Linking servant leadership to followers' thriving at work: Self-determination theory perspective. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15, Article 1384110. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1384110>
- Kristanto, H., & Hartono, S. (2024). Laissez-faire leadership style and internal communication on performance through employee engagement. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 13(9), 63–80. <https://doi.org/10.35629/8028-13096380>

- Luka, R. T., & Gofwan, D. L. (2025). Faith-based financial accountability in Nigeria: A theological perspective on stewardship in religious organizations. *International Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization*, 13(1), 8–19. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijebo.20251301.12>
- Nwanaju, I. U. (2025). Religious bigotry and good governance in Nigeria. *Public Policy and Administration Research*, 6(7), 62–68.
- Ogbe, E. B. (2025). Transformational leadership and sustainable development in Nigeria. *Kashere Journal of Politics and International Relations*, 3(2).
- Offor, E. O., Nwobashi, H. N., Emegha, K. N., & Anoke, A. U. (2025). Faith-based organisations and political development in Nigeria. *African Journal of Politics and Administrative Studies*, 18(2), 142–164. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ajpas.v18i2.9>
- Onyeulo, F. L., & Okeke, M. U. (2024). Transformational leadership for governance and development in Nigeria.
- Orgu, C. C. (2020). The Holy Spirit and power in Luke-Acts and their significance for Christian service. *KIU Journal of Humanities*, 5(2), 355–359.
- Rojahn, J., Sülzenbrück, S., & Lübke, K. (2025). Corporate debt ratios and managerial personality traits. *Corporate Ownership & Control*, 22(1), 92–102. <https://doi.org/10.22495/cocv22i1art7>
- Santiago Torner, C., González Carrasco, M., & Miranda Ayala, R. A. (2024). Ethical leadership and emotional exhaustion. *Administrative Sciences*, 14, 233. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci14090233>
- Sánchez-Soriano, M., Arango-Ramírez, P. M., Pérez-López, E. I., & García-Montalvo, I. A. (2024). Inclusive governance: Empowering communities and promoting social justice. *Frontiers in Political Science*, 6, 1478126. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpos.2024.1478126>
- Shiundu, T. W. (2024). Leadership styles and their influence on ethical decision making in organizations. *Journal of Human Resource & Leadership*, 8(1), 68–77. <https://doi.org/10.53819/81018102t30132>
- Suryawan, I. G. R., Ardana, I. K., & Suwandana, I. G. M. (2021). Transformational leadership, work stress and turnover intention. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research*, 5(1), 146–157.
- Tanugraha, Y., Yulien, F., Havish, F., & Hadi, T. (2024). Servant leadership: Biblical evidences and path to organizational effectiveness. *Indonesian Journal of Christian Education and Theology*, 3(4), 247–258. <https://doi.org/10.55927/ijcet.v3i4.11949>
- Tudor, M. (2025). What democracy does... and does not do. *Journal of Democracy*, 36(4).
- Udeagha, N., & Nwamah, G. (2023). COVID-19 pandemic: Religious leadership and the challenges of good governance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 10(9).

Zhang, L., Seong, J. Y., Hong, D. S., & Yoon, H. J. (2025). The effects of charismatic leadership on performance. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16, Article 1487886. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2025.1487886>